

Gender and Sexual Based Violence

Anwar Mhajne

Anwar Mhajne is an Associate Professor of Political Science at Stonehill College, USA. Email: amhajne@stonehill.edu

The ongoing Israel-Hamas war cannot be only examined through political, religious, or economic lenses; understanding it necessitates a thorough examination of its gender dynamics. Reports on gender-based violence, reproductive health challenges, and the weaponization of gender narratives underscore the critical need for a gender-sensitive approach to analyzing the conflict and its implications. Incorporating Feminist International Relations (IR) perspectives into Political Science frameworks can effectively address this gap (See Cockburn 2013; Nordås & Cohen 2021; Cohen 2013; Enloe 2014; Sjoberg 2016; Tickner 2011; Grey and Shepherd 2013; Plümper and Neumayer 2006; Wood 2014, Pankhurst 2014). In the case of the October 7th attacks and their aftermath, a feminist IR lens helps us understand how women's bodies have become instrumentalized and weaponized to justify violence, reject ceasefire, and draw moral distinction between victim and perpetrator.

We witnessed gender and sexual based violence become a central point of debate and mobilization in the aftermath of Hamas's October 7th attacks, when organizations such as the United Nations (UN) expressed concerns over reports of sexual violence against Israeli women during the attack (UN Women 2023, see also ARCCI 2024, UN 2024, PHR-Israel 2023). Even with UN experts asserting, "the

growing body of evidence about reported sexual violence is particularly harrowing" (OHCHR 2024a), people still questioned these allegations (Burbank 2024). The reason behind the questioning is partially due to wide disinformation and misinformation, including the unsubstantiated claims of be-headed babies (See Mhajne & Trantos 2024), and the questionable coverage of the issue by the New York Times (Boguslaw and Grim 2024). The denial also came from Hamas who criticized Western media for what they viewed as amplifying the Israeli attempts to demonize Palestinians and justify alleged war crimes in Gaza (Ahram Online 2023).

The reports of sexual violence committed by Hamas against Israeli women on October 7th were weaponized to justify the continuation of the war and to argue against a ceasefire. For instance, when the Security Council failed to pass a resolution demanding a ceasefire on December 8, 2023, Israel government spokesperson Eylon Levy tweeted: "Thank you to the United States of America for vetoing a UN Security Council resolution designed to keep Hamas' rapist regime in power." Similarly, Levy responded to South Africa's International Court of Justice Genocide case by stating in an interview to the i24News English that, "We hold South Africa criminally complicit with the Hamas rapist regime." Additionally, on February 21,

2024, the Association of Rape Crisis Centers in Israel (ARCCI) released a detailed report focusing on sexual and gender-based violence during October 7th. The report concluded that Hamas used sexual violence systematically (ARCCI 2024). It also added testimonies from hostages who were released recounting gender and sexual based violence that happened in captivity (ARCCI 2024). Linking to the news about the report, AIPAC tweeted, “A ceasefire now keeps these rapist monsters armed and in power in Gaza” (2024).

On the other hand, the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR 2024b) reported that Palestinian women and girls in detention have “been subjected to multiple forms of sexual assault, such as being stripped naked and searched by male Israeli army officers. At least two female Palestinian detainees were reportedly raped while others were reportedly threatened with rape and sexual violence.” Israel’s Mission to the UN in Geneva quickly denied the report and heavily criticized the agency. In a statement on X, formerly Twitter, the mission asserted that, “Israel forcefully rejects the despicable and unfounded claims published today by a group of so-called UN experts, including one who just days ago legitimized the massacre of October 7 in which more than 1,200 people were murdered, executed and raped, and another who publicly doubted the testimonies of Israeli victims of gender-based and sexual violence....” (2024).

The reports and the ensuing reactions to them, whether characterized by denial or endorsement, often puts women and their bodies into the heart of political discourse, serving to either validate or discredit the violence perpetrated by Hamas or Israel. Women's rights and the maltreatment of specific

groups of women are being securitized and utilized to rationalize military actions under the guise of protecting women. This securitization inherently prioritizes the protection of certain women over others, reinforcing power dynamics that favor the dominant narrative. Consequently, women who align with the perceived interests of those in power may receive more attention and support, while those who challenge or fall outside this narrative may face marginalization or even further harm. Violence against Israeli women is used to justify and perpetuate further violence on Palestinian women, and Palestinians at large.

Palestinian women and children bear a disproportionate toll of this violence, with them constituting 70% of casualties reported (UN Women 2024). Of the 2.3 million inhabitants of Gaza, about 1.9 million people are displaced, with nearly one million being women and girls seeking shelter and safety (UN Women 2024). In Gaza, limited access to medical care increases the risk of infection and maternal mortality. Newborns suffer due to unsanitary conditions and overcrowded, bombed-out medical facilities, with miscarriage rates seeing a 300% increase since the war's onset (Zhang 2024). South Africa's submissions to the International Criminal Court of Justice highlight reproductive violence in Gaza, accusing Israel of obstructing Palestinian births under Article 2(d) of the Genocide Convention (Axelson and Venkatraman, 2024). Israel's attacks on Gaza's medical infrastructure and deprivation of resources are cited as indirect measures to hinder Palestinian births (Axelson and Venkatraman, 2024).

The politicization of women's bodies in the context of conflict thus not only shapes the discourse but also affects whose suffering is recognized and validated. Furthermore, this narrative is employed to distinguish between

the 'children of light' and the 'children of darkness,' effectively separating victims from aggressors. The manipulation of narratives surrounding women's rights and victimhood serves to reinforce existing power structures and biases, influencing the allocation of resources, attention, and support. Women who do not fit neatly into the dominant narrative may find themselves overlooked or further marginalized, highlighting the complex interplay between gender, politics, and conflict. ♦

References

Ahram Online. 2023. " Hamas Condemns New York Times Allegations on Sexual Violence on 7 October." *Ahram Online*, December 31. <https://english.ahram.org.eg/News/514907.aspx>.

AIPAC. 2024. "A ceasefire now keeps these rapist monsters armed and in power in Gaza." X, February 2. <https://twitter.com/AIPAC/status/1760341184344395812>.

Axelson, Ruby Mae, and Prachiti Venkatraman. 2024. "Reproductive Violence in Palestine: The Need for a Feminist Approach to Justice." *Opinio Juris*, February 1. <https://opiniojuris.org/2024/02/01/reproductive-violence-in-palestine-the-need-for-a-feminist-approach-to-justice/>.

Boguslaw, Daniel, and Ryan Grim. 2024. "New York Times Puts 'Daily' Episode on Ice Amid Internal Firestorm over Hamas Sexual Violence Article: As the Times Faces Scrutiny for Its Coverage of Israel's War on Gaza, It Has Capitulated to the Pro-Israel Media Watchdog CAMERA." *The Intercept*. January 28. <https://theintercept.com/2024/01/28/new-york-times-daily-podcast-camera/>.

Burbank, Nick. 2024. "We deserve the truth about what happened on October 7." *Mondoweiss*. February 1. <https://mondoweiss.net/2024/02/we-deserve-the-truth-about-what-happened-on-october-7/>.

Cockburn, Cynthia. 2013. "War and security, women and gender: an overview of the issues." *Gender & Development* 21 (3): 433-452.

Cohen, Dara Kay. 2013. "Explaining rape during civil war: Cross-national evidence (1980–2009)." *American Political Science Review* 107 (3): 461-477.

Enloe, Cynthia. 2014. *Bananas, beaches and bases: Making feminist sense of international politics*. 2nd ed. Berkeley: Univ of California Press.

Grey, Rosemary, and Laura J. Shepherd. 2013. "'Stop rape now?'" Masculinity, responsibility, and conflict-related sexual violence." *Men and Masculinities* 16 (1): 115-135.

Israel's Mission to the UN in Geneva. "UN Experts Motivated by Their Hatred For Israel." Press release, February 19, 2024. Accessed February 20, 2024. URL: <https://embassies.gov.il/UNgeneva/Pages/default.aspx>.

i24NEWS English. 2024. "'We Hold South Africa Criminally Complicit with the Hamas Rapist Regime'." Interview with Eylon Levy. Published on YouTube, January 2. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1FVsyq5CViA>.

Levy, Eylon [@EylonALevy]. 2023. "Thank you to the United States for vetoing a UN Security Council resolution designed to keep the Hamas Rapist Regime in power." X, December 8. <https://twitter.com/EylonALevy/status/1733239832288059428?lang=en-GB>

- Mhajne, Anwar, and Alexandra Trantos. 2024. "Weaponising Social Media May Be Counterproductive in Hamas-Israel Conflict." *Binding Hook*, February 16. <https://binding-hook.com/articles-hooked-on-trends/weaponising-social-media-may-be-counterproductive-in-hamas-israel-conflict/>
- Nordås, Ragnhild, and Dara Kay Cohen. 2021. "Conflict-related sexual violence." *Annual Review of Political Science* 24: 193-211.
- OHCHR (Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights). 2024a. "UN Experts Demand Accountability for Victims of Sexual Torture and Unlawful Killings During 7 October Attacks." Press release, January 8. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2024/01/un-experts-demand-accountability-victims-sexual-torture-and-unlawful->
- _____. 2024b. "Israel/oPt: UN Experts Appalled by Reported Human Rights Violations Against Palestinian Women and Girls." Press release, February 19. <https://bindinghook.com/articles-hooked-on-trends/weaponising-social-media-may-be-counterproductive-in-hamas-israel-conflict/>.
- Pankhurst, Donna. 2014. "Sexual violence in war." In *Gender Matters in Global Politics*, eds. Laura Shepherd and Caitlin Hamilton, 159-170. London: Routledge.
- Physician For Human Rights-Israel (PHR-Israel). 2023. Gender-Based Violence as a Weapon of War during the October 7 Hamas Attacks | Position Paper. November. <https://www.phr.org.il/en/gender-based-violence-eng/>
- Plümper, Thomas, and Eric Neumayer. 2006. "The unequal burden of war: The effect of armed conflict on the gender gap in life expectancy." *International organization* 60 (3): 723-754.
- Sjoberg, Laura. 2016. "Gender-based violence in war." In *Handbook on Gender and War*, eds. Simona Sharoni, Julia Welland, Linda Steiner, and Jennifer Pedersen, 175-193. Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar Publishing, Inc.
- The Association of Rape Crisis Centers in Israel. 2024. "Silent Cry: Sexual Crimes in the October 7 War." February 21. https://www.gov.il/BlobFolder/news/arcci-submits-first-report-to-un-21-feb-2024/en/English_Swords_of_Iron_DOCUMENTS_ARCCI%20report%20-%20Hamas%20sexual%20crimes%20on%20october%207.pdf.
- Tickner, Ann J. (2011). "Feminist Security Studies: Celebrating an Emerging Field." *Politics and Gender* (4): 576-581.
- United Nations. 2024. Clear and convincing information' that hostages held in Gaza subjected to sexual violence, says UN Special Representative. March. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2024/03/1147217>
- UN Women. 2024. Gender Alert: The Gendered Impact of the Crisis in Gaza. January. <https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/2024-01/Gender%20Alert%20The%20Gendered%20Impact%20of%20the%20Crisis%20in%20Gaza.pdf>
- United Nations Women. 2023. "UN Women Statement on the Situation in Israel and Gaza." December 1. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/news-stories/statement/2023/12/unwomen-statement-on-the-situation-in-israel-and-gaza>.

Wood, Elisabeth Jean. 2014. "Conflict-related sexual violence and the policy implications of recent research." *International Review of the Red Cross* 96 (894): 457-478.

Zhang, Sharon. 2024. "Miscarriages in Gaza Have Skyrocketed by 300 Percent Under Israel's Siege: Every pregnant person in Gaza is at risk of having to undergo delivery in unsafe conditions." Truthout, January 18. <https://truthout.org/articles/miscarriages-in-gaza-have-skyrocketed-by-300-percent-under-israels-siege/>.